

Foreign Aid By Turkey Through The Kızılay Between 2010-2022

Türkiye'nin 2010-2022 Yılları Arasında Kızılay Aracılığı ile Yapmış Olduğu Dış Yardımlar

Hüdanur Kandış¹, Mehmet Anuştekin², Mehmet Murat Bayancuk³, Sevilay Günaydın⁴, Aydın Günaydın⁵, Fatma Karaoğlan Evran⁶

¹ Teacher, Silvan Guidance and Research Center, 0009-0008-2544-1407, Diyarbakır, Turkey.

² Guidance Teacher, Çınar Guidance and Research Center, 0000-0002-2362-4911, Diyarbakır, Turkey.

³ Institution Manager, Silvan Guidance and Research Center, 0009-0007-5932-0921, Diyarbakır, Turkey.

⁴ Class Teacher, Fatih Primary School, 0009-0008-5281-5064, Eskişehir, Türkiye.

⁵ Class Teacher, Fatih Primary School, 0009-0000-2945-0388, Eskişehir, Türkiye.

⁶ Psychological Counselor Guidance Teacher, Mehmetçik Primary School, 0009-0001-4663-0572, Diyarbakır, Turkey.

ABSTRACT

In the international system, health, education, food, access to healthy water, aid after natural disasters are called humanitarian aid. This type of aid can be in different amounts and varieties depending on the economic power of the countries that will provide aid. While foreign aid is extremely important for the countries that need aid, it can also be an indicator of soft power for the countries that provide aid. Turkey is trying to deliver humanitarian aid to countries in need of aid, located at intercontinental distances outside of the geography it is in. An important part of these aids is provided through the Turkish Red Crescent. The Turkish Red Crescent is an institution with an association status and has 16 representations around the world. The foreign aid that Turkey made through the Red Crescent between the years 2010-2022 is discussed. This study was carried out through document analysis, one of the qualitative research methods. The data of the study were collected through newspaper news, related books, articles and websites covering the period between 2010-2022. As a result of the research, it was seen that the Red Crescent took a very active role in Turkey's foreign aid, and provided various cash and in-kind aids to many countries of the world. It has been observed that Turkey provided a total of 622,699,557 ₺ foreign aid in 2022 through the Red Crescent. It is predicted that the amount of foreign aid will continue to increase with each passing year.

Keywords: Turkey, Turkish Red Crescent Association, Foreign Aid.

ÖZET

Uluslararası sistemde sağlık, eğitim, gıda, sağlıklı suya erişim, doğal afetler sonrası yapılan yardımlara insani yardım denilmektedir. Bu tür yardımlar, yardım yapacak ülkelerin ekonomik gücüne bağlı olarak farklı miktarlarda ve çeşitlerde olabilir. Dış yardım, yardıma ihtiyaç duyan ülkeler için son derece önemliken, yardım sağlayan ülkeler için de yumuşak gücün göstergesi olabiliyor. Türkiye içerisinde bulunduğu coğrafyanın dışında kıtalar arası mesafelerde bulunan yardıma ihtiyaç duyan ülkelere insani yardımları ulaştırmaya çalışmaktadır. Bu yardımların önemli bir kısmı ise Türk Kızılay'ı aracılığı ile gerçekleştirilmektedir. Türk Kızılay'ı dernek statüsünde bir kurum olup, dünya genelinde 16 temsilciliği bulunmaktadır. Türkiye'nin 2010-2022 yılları arasında Kızılay aracılığı ile yapmış olduğu dış yardımlar ele alınmıştır. Yapılan bu çalışma nitel araştırma yöntemlerinden doküman analizi yoluyla gerçekleştirilmiştir. Çalışmanın verileri 2010-2022 yılları arasındaki dönemi kapsayan gazete haberleri, ilgili kitaplar, makaleler ve internet siteleri aracılığı ile toplanmıştır. Araştırma sonucunda Türkiye'nin dış yardımlarında Kızılay'ın oldukça aktif bir rol aldığı, dünyanın pek çok ülkesine çeşitli nakdi ve aynı yardımlar yaptığı görülmüştür. Türkiye'nin Kızılay aracılığı ile 2022 yılında toplam 622.699.557 ₺ dış yardımda bulunduğu görülmüştür. Dış yardım miktarlarının her geçen yıl artarak süreceği öngörülmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Türkiye, Türk Kızılay Derneği, Dış Yardım.

INTRODUCTION

People may sometimes need the help of the others around them when they are facing with immediate and unexpected circumstances in their lives. The same goes for the states as well. Whether it is human-induced or natural disaster related, states may need humanitarian aid, namely, other countries' help when they are confronted with unexpected circumstances. This aid may include provision of search and rescue operations, shelter, food and water, clothes, healthcare, education, security, transportation etc. Foreign aid usually takes place from developed countries to underdeveloped countries. Foreign aid sometimes serves as a show of soft power or a show of strength. However, foreign aid is humanistically important.

Citation: Kandış, H., Anuştekin, M., Bayancuk, M. M., Günaydın, S. ve Günaydın, A. (2024) "Foreign aid by Turkey Through the Kızılay between 2010-2022", International QMX Journal, 3(2), 1120-1128. ISSN: 3023-6037.

Copyright © 2024 by author(s) and Scientific Research Publishing Inc. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International License (CC BY 4.0)

Turkey has also provided foreign aid as much as it could, sometimes even more than it could. The foreign aid is provided by various foundations, associations, institutions and organisations in Turkey. One of these associations is Turkish Red Crescent Association. The association's founding purpose was to tend to the soldiers who got injured in battle in the Ottoman period, taking inspiration from the red cross. However, it broadened its mission in the process of time and evolved into an association which organises all kinds of humanitarian aid services.

The Turkish Red Crescent have stood out with providing aid internationally in the recent years, along with its domestic aid. The Turkish Red Crescent has 16 permanent representations worldwide today. It provides aid to the needy via these representations. The association recorded provision of foreign aid valuing 622.699.557 ₺ varying from shelter, education, food, to non-food supplies and hygienic supplies since the year of 2022. The association is expected to increase the number of its permanent presentations, diversify the range and augment the quantity of its foreign aid in the future. The association's providing foreign aid is believed to be both essential for creating a positive image for the country and for the Turkic states.

THE CONCEPT OF FOREIGN AID

It appears that the concept of foreign aid is defined in many ways. Although it was defined as "a state's providing resources to another state" at first, various meanings have been attributed to it in the process of time, which resulted in its evolving into a richer and complex meaning (Akçay, 2012:5). Turkish Language Association (TDK) defines the concept as "any kind of monetary or needed material lent or given to a country" (www.tdk.gov.tr).

When foreign aid is spoken of, the first thing comes to mind is international economic aid. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) handles foreign aid in three categories. These are sorted as: (1) official aid provided on the purpose of cooperation and sustainable development with the low income countries, (2) financial transactions made to the affluent countries, (3) humanitarian aid provided by non governmental organisations. According to OECD's definition, foreign aid is the low interest and long-term loans, which has to consist of at least 25% donation when it is given to states, given on the purpose of enhancing the economic and social welfare of underdeveloped and developing countries (www.oecd.org/).

It can be briefly defined as "the international transfer of capital, goods, or services from a country or international organization for the benefit of the recipient country or its population" (<https://www.britannica.com>). Foreign aid can be economic, military, or emergency humanitarian.

Theoretical Dimension of Foreign Aid

First of all, states need to be present with all their institutions for the provision of aid to take place between aiding country and the recipient country. The Peace of Westphalia (1648), which is known as the treaty that finalised the thirty years war, is significant in this respect. Rise of modern nation states as a result of this treaty also brought the utilisation of foreign aid as a means of foreign politics with it. One of the major concepts that became prevalent after the Peace of Westphalia and defined the modern world system over time, sovereignty, brought the concept of border alongside. Therefore, foreign aid became the driving force to reach beyond the natural borders. Foreign aid reached a theoretical extent upon the activities that OECD carried out in 1960s. II. Although the Marshall Plan, which aimed to aid the recovery of Europe after the second world war, proposed a theoretical basis in the matter of foreign aid, its effort to create a common aid policy featured OECD (Akçay, 2012:7-8).

Foreign aid is handled in different approaches in the discipline of international affairs. It is stated that the international system has an anarchical nature, in which factors such as security, survival and power prevail, and the human nature has a tendency to war. According to realists, the prior motivation for a country to provide foreign aid is to look after its interests and seek alliances. This can be inferred from the emphasis placed on the military power. After the 9/11 attacks, foreign aid became a part of the means of international politics that states utilise, for the balance of power was divided between the two blocs in the Cold War period. These examples confirm states' utilisation of foreign aid to look after their interests as realists claimed (Akçay, 2012:9). On the other hand, neorealists handle foreign aid in the economic respect and draw attention to the existence of the potential of the recipient countries.

Idealism argues that the human nature is good in itself, and peace can be established by preventing wars. Therefore the theory, due to its being peaceful, handles foreign aid within the elements such as humanitarian values, economic development and democracy. Based on this approach, many positive approaches are discussed on many issues such as eliminating the poverty on the world, infusing democracy around the world, establishing the economic development globally. According to Marxists, foreign aid is a system, where the economic inequality between the countries with low welfare level, which are known as the third world countries, and the developed countries is preserved (Schraeder, vd., 1998:3).

Countries use their military forces to ensure their own security, to resist dangerous situations and to achieve the desired results. Using economic power is often a similarly simple use of power that takes a short time to produce results. However, using soft power is a process that requires a long and laborious process and depends on the acceptance of its followers. Using elements of soft power in foreign aid is more difficult, more common, and more costly than using elements of hard power (Nye, 2005).

In order to positively increase their image in the eyes of their target countries, countries follow a constructive and active method in their foreign policies by organizing programs that support economic development. The images of states that spend on public diplomacy increase positively, which increases their likelihood of achieving the results they aim for. Cultural elements and the support provided by the state in terms of education, expenditures made for a field in which they are good, and the promotion of all these internationally are another soft power.

Today, developing countries use economic and humanitarian aid in their foreign policies within the scope of soft power. Soft power changes the attitudes of other states' actors; Cultural interactions have gained importance when examining Turkey's soft power practices, as culture, foreign policy practices and values are the shape of the relationships to be developed with these actors. Using peaceful methods in politics and following an active policy and setting the agenda are examples of how countries use soft power (Kirişçi, 2007).

Types of Foreign Aid

There are multiple different opinions and debates in the literature about the types of foreign aid. The efficiency of foreign aid, the difference it makes, its method and purpose, amount, aided countries' geographical structures, etc. are examined in various ways. This study generally reviews them and discusses foreign aid under six main topics.

Humanitarian Aid

This aid type ranges from food aid to medicine aid carried out by non-governmental organizations and aimed to reduce the negative effects of floods, earthquakes, epidemics, natural disasters, etc. on the population. (Morgenthau, 1962:301). Apparent in its name, this aid type is humanitarian and its main purpose is to provide early intervention to problems that could lead up to global crises. Moreover, humanitarian aids could appear in the form of shows of strength on the part of aiding countries (Tüfekçi, 2016:112).

Bilateral and Multilateral Aid

This type of aid occurs as part of pacts between aided and aiding countries. Multilateral aid consists of multiple aiding/aided countries. The difference between the two is that multilateral aid is supervised not by governments, but by an international organization (Arslan ve Kiper, 2015:19).

Factors such as economic, political, historical, etc. relations between aided and aiding countries; other factors such as a direct communication between the parties, contribution to foreign politics, etc. impact this type of aid heavily. However, in cases of possible conflict or post-war development efforts, multilateral aid supervised by an international organization, thanks to its more extensive efforts, is more effective than bilateral aid (Akçay, 2012:6).

Military Aid

This type of aid is a popular one, owing to its political implications. Military aid serves purposes of improved political relations and shows of strength of defence technology. The aided country directly or

indirectly shapes its foreign policy in favour of the aiding country due to the aid (Gönlübol, 2000:153). An example would be the USA providing aid to Israel and Egypt because Israel's security is important for the USA's security.

Sometimes military aid is observed to be used as threats. 13.01.1984 saw that after the attack against marine soldiers in Lebanon, the USA included Iran in its list of State Sponsors of Terrorism. Foreign aid to Iran was to be banned, and countries that would aid Iran were deterred by threats of economic sanction (Ayhan, 2006:200).

Development Aid

This type of aid usually aims to improve the standard of living and economic conditions in underdeveloped countries. Underdeveloped countries need to invest in development. However, because they don't have the necessary capital, they procure their financial need with foreign aid (Başkaya, 2011:62).

According to OECD, aid efforts through official institutions are classified as ODA (Official Development Assistance). Also, for an aid to be classified as ODA, the primary objective must be the economic development of the country and 25% of the aid must be in the form of grant(s) (Öztürk ve Öztürk, 2012:24).

Technical Aid

Technical aid consists of information transfer from developed countries to underdeveloped countries, for better allocation of workforce sources and improved efficiency in investment opportunities. This type of aid not only aims to support economic development but also to increase the technical capacity of the country through better education and specialization. In this case, desired modern technology is transferred by developed countries to underdeveloped countries through cooperation programs (Yelek, 2020:27). For example: Turkey provides students in Africa and Turkic States both with primary education and technical training opportunities (Özmutlu, 2010:97).

Project and Program Aid

Project aid refers to grants or loans for an underdeveloped country to complete a project in a situation where their own resources are not enough to do so. Program aid, on the other hand, refers to loans with low-interest rates provided to countries struggling with financial instabilities, regardless of any projects on the agenda (Öztürk ve Öztürk, 2012:5). This type of aid includes investment projects in its scope, and positively affects recipient country's capital. Along with program grants, interim payments, and support for budget stability; industry-specific aid, fixture aid, and commodity-based financing fall under this scope (Akgün, 2009:19).

Development of Turkish Foreign Aid

Changes in Turkey's foreign policy in the past few years manifest minimized domestic and global problems, and a shift from Eurocentric and one-sided policies to alternative policies. In this aspect, the strategy of improving relations with international actors by increasing the number of interaction spaces and thus broadening the operation field internationally marks a new era for Turkey's foreign policy. Instead of age-old policies, a new system is on the horizon, including new tendencies and practices that may change the perception of Turkey in the eyes of actors of international volition. Starting from the 2000s, Turkey has been making drastic changes in its foreign policy of low-profile passiveness, and in the meantime, taking initiatives that would increase social and economic well-being. In this atmosphere of change, with the adoption of aid as an active tool for foreign politics, it can be speculated that Turkey's international recognition and reputation will increase (<https://www.mfa.gov.tr/dis-politika-genel.tr.mfa>).

According to Akçay (2012:78), the improvement in Turkey's foreign aid practices and establishing a more active, systematic basis was made possible by three important factors. First of them is TİKA being operational from 1999 onwards; second is the improved conception of Turkish Non-governmental Action after the Earthquake of 1999; and lastly, the initiative policy in Africa in 2005. It is thanks to these factors that Turkey can boast a significant improvement in its foreign aid policy. Indeed, with the

improvement on the part of NGOs, both the geographical scope and the amount of foreign aid has increased substantially (Akçay, 2012:78).

Institutions and Organizations In Turkey Providing Foreign Aid

Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency

TİKA undertakes a good part of Turkey's foreign aid efforts. Especially in the 1990s, TİKA operated on many fields including helping Turkic States that became independent after the dissolution of USSR to recover and reconstruct, protect their cultural and political rights, and overcome technical difficulties in infrastructure. TİKA was affiliated to the Prime Ministry instead of Ministry of Foreign Affairs after a change in 1999. TİKA's body of rules, jurisdiction and responsibilities were issued in the Official Gazette dated 2001 and with the law numbered 4668. Said law changed the name from "Economic, Cultural, Educational and Technical Cooperation Agency" to "Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency (TİKA)". The reason for this change is that TİKA couldn't attain the desired level of operations since its beginning and that new and various other needs emerged (Erdağ, 2015:244).

Although, in the founding years, TİKA initially focused its efforts in Central Asia mainly on development aid, later on, because of major global and regional shifts, the organizational structure of TİKA was restructured. With the Statutory Decree Law No. 656 dated October 2, 2011, the body of rules and the name of Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency (TİKA) were updated and its flexible new structure that enabled much quicker decision-making helped its activities to continue in a more robust manner (www.tika.gov.tr).

The name change gives away some clues of a future roadmap and fields of operation. In the end, despite its founding purpose was to support the development of new republics gaining their independence in the Caucasus and Central Asia, 2000s saw a change in this purpose. The new, restructured TİKA put more emphasis on soft power and humanitarian diplomacy. In this perspective, institutions and organizations serving in fields of soft power and humanitarian diplomacy such as the Red Crescent Association, Yunus Emre Institute, and Administration for Turks Living Abroad and Related Communities (YTB) have cooperated to make inter-institutional coordination more active and efficient. Financial foreign aid aiming development was replaced by projects run with cooperation of national and international organizations. Consequently, TİKA's new given purpose was to coordinate Turkey's public institutions, NGOs, national and international private organizations in reaching a common goal. TİKA, now focuses on project-based programs with the legislative changes, based its operations on creating projects or supporting existing projects in this direction. Accordingly, the support orbits around fields of education, health, IT, economy, agriculture, etc. Moreover, it supports projects on foreign language education, cultural and art activities such as conferences, exhibitions, etc. and restoration of Turkic relics (Aktaş, 2021:88).

Thanks to TİKA, Turkey not only operated for related communities but also changed its view on foreign policy. Especially since 2000s, coupled with the increase in economic well-being, Turkey has placed itself in the providing end of aid. TİKA, today, with 62 Program Coordination Offices in 60 countries, continues its operations in 150 countries (www.tika.gov.tr).

Disaster and Emergency Management Authority (AFAD)

[Turkey General Directorate of Emergency Management, affiliate of Ministry of Interior, and General Directorate of Natural Disasters were shut down in 2009 to be merged. Later in 2018, it was relocated under Prime Ministry as Disaster and Emergency Management Authority (www.afad.gov.tr).

AFAD continues relief efforts both domestically and internationally. AFAD's foreign aid considered, its relief efforts in natural disasters and public disturbances occurring all around the world are especially important. For example, a sum of 3.477.752 ₺ was raised by AFAD for the Muslim population in Myanmar who were suffering from famine and poverty after the internal conflicts in Myanmar in 2012. Likewise, 2.500 food packages and 6 tons of medicine were provided to the Yemen public after the civil war. (www.trthaber.com).

The flood and earthquake in Afghanistan in 2014 affected Jowzjan and Sar-e Pol. AFAD provided 223 tons of food supply for 3.000 families who suffered. (www.aa.com.tr) After the Earthquake in Nepal in 2015, 26 members of AFAD joined the search and rescue efforts. (Hürriyet Gazetesi, 26.04.2015).

Yunus Emre Institute (YEE) and its foreign aid actions

Yunus Emre Institute was named after Yunus Emre, who was an Anatolian Sufi living in the 13th and 14th centuries. His most important feature is that he is a symbol of human values, human love and social peace. Yunus Emre Institute was initially founded as an institution affiliated to Yunus Emre Foundation under the law dated 05.05.2007 and numbered 5653. The primary objective of the Foundation is to promote Turkish language, culture, history and art (www.yee.org.tr)

Yunus Emre Institution, in cooperation with other nations, operates activities related to language, culture, art, and science. In 2019, with the "Mobile Mathematics Museum" project, the Institution provided aid for 60.000 Syrian children who have taken refuge in Turkey. Moreover, a class was provided in Solfasol Primary School in Ankara for Syrians to learn Turkish. (YEE, 2019:10-34)

In 19.08.2011, President Recep Tayyip Erdoğan's visit to Somalia removed the isolation barrier between the two countries. Accordingly, since 2011, Turkey has been investing in education, security, transportation, etc. in Somalia. In 2017, the Somalian Army was provided training and 300 students were given Turkish classes under 8 lecturers (YEE, 2019:32-34).

The Red Crescent (of Turkey)

The Red Crescent, one of the few associations whose existence spans from the Ottoman Empire, was founded in 22.08.1864. The foundation of Red Crescent is traced back to Geneva Convention. The Convention enabled for an institution similar to Red Cross to be founded. Abdullah Bey, lecturer from the Medical School, attended the International Red Cross Conference in Paris in 1867 as delegate of Ottoman Empire. Accordingly, with Abdullah Bey's support, "Ottoman Aid for Wounded and Sick Soldiers Society" was founded with 66 members, but it failed. The society dissolved in 1874 (Çapa, 2010:10-12).

Before the Russo-Turkish War, with the importance and benefit of the Red Cross understood, the society was to be revitalized after being inactive for two years. Compared to the Red Cross aid the Slav soldiers received in Balkan skirmishes in 1876, Ottoman soldiers were helpless. In the same period, France's "Mecruhin-i Askeriye İanesi Merkez Komitesi" (sic) Second Deputy Henri Dunant wrote in his letter to doctor Dikran Peştemalcıyan that after the Geneva Convention, the Ottoman Empire could utilize Red Cross and that a society should be designated in Istanbul accordingly. However, the Red Cross emblem was frowned upon by the Muslim population, and consequently, with Crimean Aziz Bey's initiative, "a red crescent upon white" as the emblem was proposed to the International Committee of the Red Cross and it was accepted on the condition that it would operate in accordance with the Red Cross. Thus, the Ottoman Red Crescent Society was officially founded on April 14, 1877 (Akgün ve Uluğtekin, 2002:23-27).

The society went through name changes in 1923, 1935, and finally in 1974 as the "Turkish Red Crescent Association" (www.kizilay.org.tr). The Association follows the Red Cross-Red Crescent principles on operation. These principles are listed as the following:

- ✓ "Humanity: The International Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement, born of a desire to bring assistance without discrimination to the wounded on the battlefield, endeavors, in its international and national capacity, to prevent and alleviate human suffering wherever it may be found. Its purpose is to protect life and health and to ensure respect for the human being. It promotes mutual understanding, friendship, cooperation and lasting peace amongst all peoples".
- ✓ "Impartiality: It makes no discrimination as to nationality, race, religious beliefs, class or political opinions. It endeavors to relieve the suffering of individuals, being guided solely by their needs, and to give priority to the most urgent cases of distress".
- ✓ "Neutrality: In order to continue to enjoy the confidence of all, the Movement may not take sides in hostilities or engage at any time in controversies of a political, racial, religious or ideological nature".
- ✓ "Independence: The Red Crescent Movement is independent. The Turkish Red Crescent Society, while an auxiliary in the humanitarian services of its government and subject to the laws of Republic

of Turkey, always maintains its autonomy so that it is able at all times to act in accordance with the principles of the International Federation of Red Crescent-Red Cross Movement".

- ✓ "Voluntary service: It is a voluntary relief movement not prompted in any manner by desire for gain".
- ✓ "Unity: There can be only one Red Crescent Society in Turkey. It must be open to all. It must carry on its humanitarian work throughout the territory of Turkiye".
- ✓ "Universality: The International Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement, in which all Societies have equal status and share equal responsibilities and duties in helping each other, is worldwide". (Official Gazette, 19.02.2009).

The Red Crescent's Foreign Aid Operations

The Red Crescent carries out its operations without discriminating people in any terms. It helps millions in need of help in many different parts on the world and carries on its works as a global factor in the matter of humanitarian aid with its ever-increasing operations day by day. The Turkish Red Crescent, whether it is a human-induced or a natural disaster, designs projects on many issues such as nutrition, shelter and development for the people in need. The Red Crescent, which provided aid to 151 countries from its foundation to the year of 2018, has 11 representations in the countries of Somalia, South Sudan, Yemen, Palestine, Afghanistan, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Iraq, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus. While the association carries out its operations in the fields such as construction of schools, community centres, sanctuaries; education, healthcare, agriculture, social aid, it also carries on its works on disaster management capacity abroad. The Red Crescent provided aid to 5.650.000 people in 28 different countries in 2016, 6.850.000 people in 38 countries in 2017, and 7.000.000 people in 53 countries in 2018 (2018:26-29).

In 2019, The Red Crescent helped 8.250.000 people in 71 countries, and increased the number of its representations to 15 via opening new ones in Myanmar, Sudan, and Indonesia (2019:27). These examples above can be to the foreign aid that The Red Crescent provided in 2019:

- ✓ 2 truck loads of clothes were sent to Georgia to provide the needy.
- ✓ 400 boxes of clothes and 100 wheelchairs were sent to the red cross in Kosovo and to the Turkish consulate general in Prizren.
- ✓ Various clothing materials were transported to Northern Macedonia and distributed to the people in need.
- ✓ 63 hearing aids were distributed to the hearing-impaired people living in the Gagauzian Autonomous Region in Moldova.
- ✓ 850 boxes of food were sent to be distributed to the needy after the flood disaster in Mauritania.
- ✓ 60.055 boxes of food were sent to the people in 38 countries in the month of Ramadan. In the Festival of Sacrifice, the meat gathered from the sacrificed animals were distributed among 114.678 people in 50 countries.
- ✓ Medical supplies valuing 69.112\$ were transported to Serbia, and also 4 truck loads of medical devices and supplies were given to Novi Pazar Public Hospital in Serbia.
- ✓ Various medical supplies valuing 73.442\$ were sent to Jordan.
- ✓ In 2020, The Red Crescent reached out to 8.250.000 people in 57 countries, and with the participation of Senegal, the association increased the number of its representations to 16 (2020:128-129). The aid operations The Red Crescent carried out in 2020 can be sorted out below:
- ✓ 2 truck loads of humanitarian aid supplies were sent to the people in need in Albania in 2019, right after the earthquake took place.
- ✓ To help the families in Cambodia affected by the floods due to heavy rain and Covid-19, financial aid of 160.000€ was provided to the red cross in Cambodia.
- ✓ Clothing materials, 30 wheelchairs, and 10.000 medical masks were sent to Kosovo, in cooperation with the Kosovan red cross.
- ✓ After the explosion took places in Beyrut, Lebanon, 1.152 blood bags, 10.000 surgical masks, 1.000 hazmat suits, 100 protective glasses, 20.000 vinyl hand wears and 50 boxes of food were sent there.

In 2022, The Red Crescent reached out to 8.515.419 people while struggling against poverty and hunger abroad. Within this scope, the association helped 353.068 people to find shelter, 5.179.259 people to get food, 115.528 people to get fresh water, 1.080.575 people to access food banks, and 1.786.989 people

to fulfill their various needs. Besides, 16 wells opened in Chad, Senegal, Sudan, and Uganda enabled 80.000 people to access fresh water. The total number of social aid beneficiaries abroad of The Red Crescent is 2.559.548. In addition, The Red Crescent has 9.370 shelters abroad (www.kizilay.org.tr).

Table 1: The Red Crescent's Cross-border Shipments in 2022

Sector/Sub-sector	Amount	Price (₺)
Shelter	1.519	30.410.248,81
Education	133,276	4.924.538,91
Food	157.494.096	362.378.542,71
Non-food Supply	18.263.714	201.507.520,24
Health	526,955	16.301.206,88
Water, Sanitation, Hygiene	482,799	7.177.499,72
TOTAL	176.902.359	622.699.557,27

Source: www.kizilay.gov.tr.

In 2022; 4 camps, 3 orphanages were founded in Idlib; 1 camp, 2 orphanages were founded and 9.370 shelters were provided for 44.728 in need in the Euphrates Shield operation area.

CONCLUSION

The modern notion of nation-states and Peace of Westphalia in 1648, seen as the foundation of diplomacy, both ended religious upheaval in Europe and accelerated interstate relations and trade operations. This advancement affected foreign aid operations, too. Consequently, foreign aid has been of effect, toward the end of the 19th century, in the decline of empires and founding of states. However, the actual leap in foreign aid coincides with the Post-WW2 period. During the power struggle of bipolar parties, foreign aid such as the Truman Doctrine and Marshall Plan proved to be very effective soft power tools.

Affiliate to OECD, Development Aid Committee's aid efforts paved the way for foreign aid to be international and institutional. Thus, foreign aid was made possible to be carried out in accordance with criteria and principles. In conducting foreign aid, ministries of foreign affairs or similar policy-making ministries and international aid organizations play a vital role in cooperation and communication. Especially with the universal principles provided by the UN and Millennium Development Goals announced in 2000, humanitarian aid was used to battle against famines, global pandemics, and disasters. Said aid was recognized by many countries and evolved into a global policy, and provided exemplary work in foreign aid.

The strong relationship between foreign aid and soft power, which is described as a foreign policy instrument, also has a very important place. Turkey has adopted the tolerance and helpful attitude of the Ottoman Empire towards all communities without discrimination as a legacy. Fulfilling the requirements of this legacy and extending a helping hand to sister geographies when even our own economy is in a difficult situation determines the line on which today's Turkish foreign aid policy will proceed. A Turkish foreign aid policy that does not have colonialist aims and does not discriminate between sects is naturally met with sympathy in the international environment. Turkish Red Crescent continues its aid activities all over the world in the context of soft power.

Turkey follows the Ottoman Empire's steps in seeing the importance of charity and tolerance. Fulfilling the demands of this legacy and lending a helping hand to others even in our own hardship shapes the modern Turkish foreign aid policy. Free of colonial purposes, or religious and racial discrimination, Turkish foreign policy is embraced globally. Turkey's leading institution in foreign aid is the Turkish Red Crescent. The Turkish Red Crescent conducted to transport the Turkish foreign aid to Somalia, Chad, Senegal, Sudan, Uganda, Lebanon, Kosovo, Cambodia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and many other countries. The efforts up until now include education, health, food, clothing, transportation, digging of wells, etc. and are bound to continue. In terms of foreign aid, the Red Crescent is as important in humanitarian aid as it is important in improving Turkey's reputation and recognition.

SOURCES

Akçay, E. (2012). *Bir Dış Politika Enstrümanı Olarak Türk Dış Yardımları*, Ankara: Turgut Özal Üniversitesi Yayınları.

Akgün B. (2009). "Türk Dış Politikası ve Uluslararası Örgütler", *Akademik Ortadoğu*, Cilt 3, Sayı 2.

- Akgün, S. K. ve Uluğtekin, M. (2002). *Hilal-i Ahmer'den Kızılay'a*. Kızılay Yayınları, Ankara.
- Aktaş, A. (2021). *Halkla İlişkiler Bağlamında İnsani Diplomasi Aracı Olarak TİKA'nın Kırgızistan'daki Çalışmaları*. Yayımlanmamış Doktora Tezi. Kırgızistan-Turkey Manas Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Bişkek.
- Arslan, E. & Kiper, K. (2015). Dış Yardım Nedir? Niçin Yapılır? *Sosyal Politika Çalışmaları Dergisi*, 0 (34).
- Ayhan, V. (2006). “Hegemonya Politikası Bağlamında ABD-İran İlişkilerinin Analizi”, *Avrasya Dosyası*, 12(2): 200-223.
- Başkaya, F. (2011). *Kalkınma İktisadının Yükselişi ve Düşüşü*. İmge Kitabevi Yayınları, Ankara.
- Çapa, M. (2010). *Kızılay (Hilal-i Ahmer) Cemiyeti (1914-1925)*. Turkey Kızılay Derneği Yayınları, Ankara.
- Erdağ, R. (2015). “Turkey'nin Kalkınma Yardımları ve TİKA”, M. Şahin ve B. S. Çevik (Ed.), *Türk Dış Politikası ve Kamu Diplomasisi*. Nobel Yayınları, Ankara, 241-262.
- Gönlübol, M. (2000). *Uluslararası Politika*. Siyasal Kitabevi, Ankara.
- Hürriyet Gazetesi, 26.04.2015.
- Kirişçi, K. (2007). Yumuşak güç aracı olarak daha dostça bir şengen vize sistemi: Türkiye'nin Deneyimi, *Uluslararası İlişkiler*, Cilt: 4, Sayı: 13.
- Morgenthau, H. (1962). A political theory of foreign aid. *The American Political Science Review*. 56 (2), 301-309.
- Nye, J. S. (2005). *Yumuşak güç*, Ankara: Elips Kitap.
- Özmutlu, S.T. (2010). *Az Gelişmiş Ülkelere Yapılan Uluslararası Yardımlar: Ekonomik ve Siyasal Boyutları*. Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi. İstanbul Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
- Öztürk, H. ve Öztürk, S. (2012). *Turkey'nin Dış Yardım Stratejisi Sorunlar ve Öneriler* (Rapor No: 54). Bilgesam. İstanbul.
- Schraeder P. J., Hook, S. W. ve Taylor, B. (1998). “Clarifying the Foreign Aid Puzzle: A Comparison of American, Japanese, French, and Swedish Aid Flows”. *World Politics*, 50(2): 294-323.
- Tüfekçi, Ö. (2016), ‘Yükselen Güçler ve Dış Politika Aracı Olarak Dış Yardımlar’, Erman Akıllı (Ed.), *Turkey'de ve Dünyada Dış Yardımlar*, (s. 101-119), Ankara: Nobel Yayıncılık.
- www.aa.com.tr, 23.06.2023.
- www.afad.gov.tr, 23.06.2023.
- www.britannica.com, 23.06.2023.
- www.kizilay.org.tr, 23.06.2023.
- www.mfa.gov.tr/dis-politika-genel.tr.mfa, 23.06.2023.
- www.oecd.org/, 23.06.2023.
- www.tika.gov.tr, 23.06.2023.
- www.trthaber.com, 23.06.2023.
- www.yee.org.tr, 23.06.2023.
- Yelek, H. (2020). *Turkey'nin Dış Yardım Politikası: Suriye Örneği*. Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi. İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
- Yunus Emre Enstitüsü, (2019). “2019 Ocak-Şubat Bülteni”. *Yunus Emre Enstitüsü Yayınları*, (52):1-56.